

List of Asses containing the 30m Mixed Landsat Image Time Series

The following GEE script can be used to extract the Asset Name and explore the data:

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/3b84f3360e8e84d75c60f479b4d16bab>

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Each file contains one band per year between 2000 and 2023 with NDVI values, access using country names can also be found here:

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var Antigua_and_Barbuda = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Antigua_and_Barbuda_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Bahamas = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Bahamas_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Bahrain = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Bahrain_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Barbados = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Barbados_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Belize = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Belize_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Cape_Verde = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Cape_Verde_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Comoros = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Comoros_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Cook_Islands = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Cook_Islands_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Cuba = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Cuba_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Dominica = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Dominica_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Dominican_Republic = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Dominican_Republic_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Fiji = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Fiji_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Grenada = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Grenada_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Guinea_Bissau = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Guinea-Bissau_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Guyana = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Guyana_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Haiti = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Haiti_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Jamaica = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Jamaica_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Kiribati = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Kiribati_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Maldives = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Maldives_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Marshall_Islands = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Marshall_Islands_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Mauritius = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Mauritius_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Micronesia = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Micronesia_Federated_States_of_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Nauru = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Nauru_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Niue = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Niue_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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var Palau = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Palau_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Papua_New_Guinea = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Papua_New_Guinea_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Saint_Kitts_and_Nevis = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Saint_Kitts_and_Nevis_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Saint_Lucia = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Saint_Lucia_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Saint_Vincent_and_the_Grenadines = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Saint_Vincent_and_the_Grenadines_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Samoa = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Samoa_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Sao_Tome_and_Principe = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Sao_Tome_and_Principe_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Seychelles = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Seychelles_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Singapore = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Singapore_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Solomon_Islands = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Solomon_Islands_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Suriname = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Suriname_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Timor_Leste = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Timor-Leste_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Tonga = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Tonga_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Trinidad_and_Tobago = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Trinidad_and_Tobago_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Tuvalu = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Tuvalu_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
var Vanuatu = ee.Image('projects/apacheta-lpd/assets/NDVI/MIXED/NDVI_MIXED_Vanuatu_2000_2023_v1_GapFillSpatial');
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